

A Comparative Study of Bupivacaine Vs Bupivacaine Plus Ketamine (Intrathecal) During Intraoperative and Postoperative Period in Non-Pregnancy Induced Hypertension Caesarean Section

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Abstract

Introduction: Postoperative pain has a significant effect on patient recovery after performing a caesarean section. The research in postoperative management has for more than two decades centered on delivery methods, pharmacotherapy with new drugs or a combination of old drugs, and organizational aspects.

Aim: The aim of my study was to evaluate the effect of intrathecal ketamine (25 mg) in parturient undergoing caesarean section added with bupivacaine (0.5%) spinal anesthesia on the onset, duration, and recovery of sensory and motor block.

Materials and Methods: A randomized double-blind trial was conducted among patients undergoing elective and emergency caesarean in a tertiary healthcare center. Informed consent was obtained by all participants. After applying the inclusion and exclusion criteria, 80 patients were involved in the present study and were assigned into 2 groups with 50 patients each. Baseline heart rate, blood pressure, respiratory rate and SpO₂ was measured. Nausea and vomiting, heart rate, blood pressure, analgesia requirement and return of motor function assessed every 30 minutes until complete recovery was assessed using Bromage scale and sedation was assessed using the Ramsay sedation scale.

Results: Time taken for sensory level to reach T5 was found to be statistically highly significant between the two groups ($p=0.000$). The mean SBP, DBP and MAP was also significantly different between the two groups when reported at the 5-minute and 10-minute time points with group B showing higher pressure values ($p<0.05$). Duration of analgesia was 2 hours 52 minutes in group A and 3 hours 27 minutes in group B with this difference being statistically significant ($p=0.000$). The difference in total number of analgesia intervention administered postoperatively was not found to be statistically significant ($p=0.262$).

Conclusion: The results obtained in the present study showed that the incidence of hypotension is drastically reduced after adding ketamine to intrathecal bupivacaine. Duration of spinal analgesia is longer with intrathecal bupivacaine plus ketamine than bupivacaine alone. There were also no side effects on neonate by adding ketamine to intrathecal bupivacaine.

Keywords: Bupivacaine, Caesarean Section, Ketamine, Postoperative pain.

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Introduction

Ketamine use has been a contentious issue since it was first introduced in the middle of the 1960s. When it first came to prospective applications, there was a lot of excitement. But anxieties surfaced, restricting availability and impeding distribution. Still, ketamine has garnered more attention lately, particularly in the fields of psychiatry and emergency care, among others.[1]

Epidural and intrathecal methods have been demonstrated to be efficient in administering ketamine, a powerful anesthetic with analgesic effects. [3] "Dissociative anesthesia" is a special

kind of anesthesia that can be brought on by ketamine. In this state, patients look awake but are unresponsive to obvious surgical stimuli.[2] Its mode of action involves both local anesthetic effects and non-competitive antagonistic effects at N methyl D aspartate (NMDA) receptors. It activates the respiratory and cardiovascular systems, giving it a distinct benefit over traditional local anesthetics. [3,7] But there are also notable side effects linked to ketamine treatment, such as delirium and hallucinations, which may restrict its usefulness.[4]

Surgical treatments such as cesarean sections are widely performed worldwide; in certain nations, they even make up as much as 60% of births. Hemostasis, surgical site infection, incision site opening, and pain are among the side effects that are rising in tandem with the rates of cesarean sections. Because of the development of neuroendocrine reflexes and increased sympathetic tone, pain following a cesarean section can result in complications such as weakened immune system, increased oxygen consumption by the heart, reactive hypoglycemia that delays wound healing, paralytic ileus, and decreasing respiratory function. Nursing and the care of the mother and baby depend on the control of pain and the acceleration of wound healing following cesarean delivery. Numerous medications used for this purpose have negative effects, such as nausea, respiratory discomfort, gastrointestinal bleeding, and itching, particularly opiates and nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory medicines (NSAIDs).[5]

Opioid usage, chronic pain, and postpartum depression can all worsen if pain during the postpartum period is not managed. Opioids delivered via spinal or epidural pathways are the basis of initial postoperative pain management following cesarean delivery. Systemic opioids should only be used for pain that cannot be adequately managed with nonopioid drugs, as the evidence does not clearly support their superiority in these situations.[6]

Because it may occupy the pathway of central sensitization and subsequent postoperative hyperalgesia, ketamine has been suggested as a part of multimodal analgesia for a variety of surgical operations. Ketamine's efficacy as an adjuvant medicine to the usual opioid regimen is demonstrated at subanesthetic doses, where it has no undesirable side effects and a notable analgesic and opioid-sparing effect. [8,9]

However, a lack of evidence on the effectiveness of ketamine uses in reducing the different aftereffects of cesarean sections has resulted in a lack of its implementation and is the cornerstone for the conduction of the present study. The study was conducted with the aim to evaluate the effect of intrathecal ketamine (25 mg) in parturient undergoing caesarean section added with bupivacaine (0.5%) spinal anesthesia on the onset, duration and recovery of sensory and motor block; intra-operative hemodynamic stability, to evaluate the protective effect of ketamine on new born baby and to observe the duration of post operative analgesia, the incidence of side effects and cardiovascular effects of intrathecal ketamine.

Material and Methods

The present study was a randomized double-blind trial conducted among patients undergoing

caesarean section in tertiary healthcare center, Shri Sathya Sai Medical College and Research Institute, Puducherry. The study was conducted after obtaining clearance from the Institutional Human Ethics Committee (IHEC) and were registered as a clinical trial on the Clinical Trial Registry of India (CTRI). Informed consent was obtained by all participants that participated in the present study.

Patients were included in the study if they were aged between 20 to 35 years, belonged to ASA class I or II, had an SBP between 100-139 mm of Hg as well as a DBP of 60-89 mm of Hg. Patients who refused treatment, known cases of pregnancy induced hypertension, patients with medical complications like severe anaemia, severe hypovolemic shock, and septicemia or with abnormal BTCT or on anti-coagulant therapy. Patients with wound infection at the site of injection (Lumbar puncture) or any evidence of foetal compromise were excluded from the present study.

Sample Size Estimation

Procedure

After applying the inclusion and exclusion criteria, 80 patients were involved in the present study and were assigned into 2 groups with 50 patients each. Group A received 1.8 cc Bupivacaine (0.5%) with normal saline (0.5 cc) and Group B received 1.8 cc of 0.5% bupivacaine along with 25 mg preservative free ketamine (0.5 cc). Patient allocation was done by computer generated randomization table and sealed cover method.

Baseline heart rate, blood pressure, respiratory rate and SpO₂ was measured. After that, lumbar puncture was done by 25-gauge Quincke spinal needle in L3-4 or L4-5 inter-space. Spinal anaesthesia was given in group A with bupivacaine 0.5% 1.8ml + 0.5ml normal saline, Group B with bupivacaine 0.5% 1.8ml + ketamine 25 mg (0.5ml). Left uterine tilt was given using a wedge under the right hip. Sensory level was determined by a pin prick. O₂ 6 liters by Hudson mask was administered till the delivery of the baby.

All patients were then monitored for anesthesia and analgesia up to 24 hours post-operatively and visual analogue scale was used for evaluating pain. Sedation of the patient was also evaluated along with heart rate, NIBP, oxygen saturation monitored and duration of sensory and motor was recorded. IM Injection Diclofenac (75 mg) was given as a rescue analgesic when the patient perceived pain, Injection Tramadol 100 mg IM was given after two doses of Diclofenac. Number of rescue analgesics in 24 Hours of post-operative period was recorded.

If maternal systolic pressure dropped below 100 mmHg or more than 20% baseline, it was treated with IV fluids and IV ephedrine. Any intra-

operative significant bradycardia from baseline was treated with IV atropine. Nausea and vomiting, heart rate, blood pressure, analgesia requirement and return of motor function assessed every 30 minutes until complete recovery was assessed using Bromage scale and sedation was assessed using the Ramsay sedation scale.

Statistical Analysis

Data was analyzed using SPSS software version 24.0. Categorical variables are presented in a frequency table, and continuous variables are presented in mean \pm SD form. Quantitative data was analyzed by student's t-test and qualitative

data was analyzed using Chi-square test. A p-value < 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results

Eighty patients belonging to ASA I and II of either sex aged between 20-35 years, posted for emergency and elective LSCS surgery under spinal anesthesia were selected for the study. The results from table 1 showed that the mean age, weight, and height between the two groups was comparable. Time taken for sensory level to reach T5 was 6.15 ± 1.33 for group A and 3.50 ± 1.24 for group B and this difference was found to be statistically highly significant ($p=0.000$).

Table 1: Mean age, weight, height, and time for sensory level to reach T5

Variable	Study group	Mean \pm SD	t* value	p-value
Age (years)	Group A	25.7 \pm 3.94	0.181	0.857
	Group B	25.5 \pm 3.48		
Weight (kilograms)	Group A	63.52 \pm 5.32	-0.019	0.985
	Group B	63.55 \pm 6.65		
Height (centimeters)	Group A	157.7 \pm 5.20	0.560	0.577
	Group B	157.05 \pm 5.19		
Time for sensory level to reach T5	Group A	6.15 \pm 1.3311	9.212	0.000*
	Group B	3.50 \pm 1.2403		

Results related to the incidence of hypotension showed that hypotension was observed among 26 participants in group A and 7 patients in group B while 14 and 33 patients in group A and B respectively were non hypertensive and this difference was found to be statistically highly significant ($p=0.000$). Episodes of hypotension was also assessed between the two groups and the results

showed that group A patients reported with 0,1,2 and 3 episodes among 14,18,6 and 2 patients respectively while 33 patients in group B reported no episodes of hypertension while 7 patients reported a single episode of hypertension, and this difference was found to be statistically highly significant ($p=0.000$).

Table 2: Incidence and number of episodes of hypertension

	Variables	Group A (N=40)	Group B (N=40)	Chi Square	p-value
Variables	Hypotension	26	7	18.620	0.000*
	Absence of Hypotension	14	33		
No of episodes	0	14	33	20.521	0.000*
	1	18	7		
	2	6	-		
	3	2	-		

*Statistically significant ($p<0.05$)

Results related to heart rate showed that at 2 minutes, the heart rate was 107.9 ± 6.01 bpm in group A and 97.6 ± 10.4 bpm in group B and this difference was found to be statistically significant ($p=0.000$). At 10 minutes, group A reported a heart rate of 87.6 ± 5.53 bpm in group A and 95.8 ± 6.15 bpm in group B. Fifteen-minute time point showed that group A had a heart rate of 85.2 ± 4.71 bpm and

group B had a heart rate of 94.4 ± 3.95 bpm in group B which was significantly different ($p=0.000$). Similar significant differences were seen with respect to heart rate at 20 min, 30 min, 40 min and 50 min time points with $p=0.000$. This difference was not significant at the 60 mins, 75 min and 90 min time point ($p>0.05$) [Table 3].

Table 3: Changes in heart rate between two groups at various intervals of follow-up

Time (min)	Group A	Group B	df	t test	P Value
Baseline	100.1±6.0	97.9±10.3	78	1.167	0.247
2 min	107.9±6.01	97.6±10.4	78	5.463	0.000*
5 min	100.7±5.39	101.2±9.13	78	-0.328	0.744
10 min	87.6±5.53	95.8±6.15	78	-6.251	0.000*
15 min	85.2±4.71	94.4±3.95	78	-9.486	0.000*
20 min	79.1±6.79	90.4±4.57	78	-8.671	0.000*
30 min	77.7±5.55	86.7±4.39	78	-8.044	0.000*
40 min	72.7±6.16	79.2±3.86	78	-5.677	0.000*
50 min	71.1±6.86	75.8±3.87	78	-3.732	0.000*
60 min	72.9±7.64	75.6±3.47	74	-1.877	0.064
75 min	75.4±8.35	75.6±6.09	11	-0.056	0.956
90 min	67±4.24	76±0	2	-3.00	0.095

* Statistically significant (p<0.05)

In group A, the mean systolic blood pressure was 93.5±13.6 mm of Hg and 104.3±8.81 mm of Hg in group B at the 5-minute time point and this difference was statistically significant (p=0.000). At the 10-minute time point, the values were 95.7±11.5 mm of Hg for group A and 103.5±8.17 mm of Hg in group B with this difference being statistically significant (p=0.001) [Table 4]. Results with regard to diastolic blood pressure showed that 48.6±10.2 mm of Hg in group A and 60.9±10.1 mm of Hg in group B and this difference was statistically significant (p=0.000) at the 5-minute time point. At the

10-minute time point, 52.3±9.77 mm of Hg was reported in group A and 56.6±7.65 mm of Hg in group B with this difference being statistically significant (p=0.034) [Table 5]. Results related to mean arterial pressure showed that at the 5 minutes, group A had a pressure of 63.3±10.9 mm of Hg and 74.6±7.62 mm of Hg in group B and this difference was found to be statistically significant (p=0.000). At 10-minutes, the mean arterial pressure was 66.7±9.74 mm of Hg in group A and 72.7±6.67 mm of Hg in group B with this difference being statistically significant (p=0.002) [Table 6].

Table 4: Changes in systolic blood pressure between two groups at various intervals of follow-up

Time (Min)	Group A	Group B	df	t-test	p-value
Baseline	118.8±8.86	120.4±10.9	78	-0.720	0.473
2 min	108±8.15	108.5±9.39	78	-0.267	0.790
5 min	93.5±13.6	104.3±8.81	78	-4.227	0.000*
10 min	95.7±11.5	103.5±8.17	78	-3.527	0.001*
15 min	101.1±10.9	104.1±7.14	78	-1.422	0.159
20 min	102.1±5.83	103.1±6.22	78	-0.779	0.438
30 min	103.2±7.66	104.5±6.45	78	-0.837	0.405
40 min	104.6±5.99	104.7±6.36	78	-0.054	0.957
50 min	104.4±3.47	104.7±6.77	77	-1.732	0.087
60 min	105.1±3.59	106.8±7.13	71	-1.301	0.197
75 min	106.2±3.96	112.7±10.4	11	-1.330	0.210
90 min	109.5±4.95	109.5±6.36	2	0.000	1.000

*Statistically significant (p<0.05)

Table 5: Changes in diastolic blood pressure between two groups at various intervals of follow-up

Time (Min)	Group A	Group B	df	t-test	p-value
Baseline	72.02±10.1	70.2±9.75	78	0.821	0.414
2 min	59.2±9.37	59.3±9.85	78	-0.070	0.945
5 min	48.6±10.2	60.9±10.1	78	-5.433	0.000*
10 min	52.3±9.77	56.6±7.65	78	-2.153	0.034*
15 min	57.9±8.78	57.7±8.52	78	0.142	0.887
20 min	55.2±6.88	56.7±6.28	78	-1.018	0.312
30 min	55.5±7.86	57.2±6.57	78	-1.049	0.297
40 min	58.7±7.51	56.4±7.75	78	1.363	0.177
50 min	58.7±7.77	59.3±10.6	77	-0.279	0.781
60 min	59±6.48	58.9±8.80	71	0.049	0.961
75 min	60±10.3	65.6±9.66	11	-0.996	0.341

*Statistically significant (p<0.05)

Table 6: Changes in mean arterial blood pressure between two groups at various intervals of follow-up

Time (Min)	Group A	Group B	df	t test	P Value
Baseline	87.5±8.72	85.9±10.6	78	0.737	0.463
2 min	75.1±7.85	75.6±8.93	78	-0.293	0.771
5 min	63.3±10.9	74.6±7.62	78	-5.359	0.000*
10 min	66.7±9.74	72.7±6.67	78	-3.240	0.002*
15 min	72.6±8.79	73.1±7.16	78	-0.265	0.792
20 min	71±5.97	72.7±5.45	78	-1.369	0.175
30 min	71.5±6.47	72.9±5.58	78	-1.018	0.312
40 min	73.7±5.44	72.5±6.29	78	0.951	0.345
50 min	73.8±6.34	73.7±6.73	77	0.056	0.955
60 min	74±4.52	73.8±7.10	71	0.107	0.915
75 min	76.2±8.68	77.4±10.1	11	-0.215	0.834
90 min	83±5.66	71.5±3.53	2	2.438	0.135

*Statistically significant (p<0.05)

Table 7: Average intraoperative SPO₂ between two groups at various intervals of follow-up

Time (Min)	Group A	Group B	df	t test	P Value
0	98.05±0.876	97.9±0.904	78	0.502	0.617
10	99.5±0.506	99.55±0.552	78	-0.422	0.674
20	99.4±0.709	99.38±0.705	78	0.158	0.875
30	99.3±0.797	99.2±0.758	78	0.719	0.474
40	99.3±0.784	99.2±0.853	78	0.409	0.683
50	99.1±0.791	99.05±0.714	78	0.445	0.657
60	98.5±0.905	98.6±0.979	78	-0.711	0.479
90	97.9±0.928	97.88±0.883	78	0.123	0.902

*Statistically significant (p<0.05)

Average intraoperative SPO₂ was recorded and the results showed that there was no statistically significant difference in the values at any time point between 0 to 90 minutes [Table 7].

APGAR score at the first minute was recorded and the analysis showed that most of the patients were normal (35 and 36 respectively) and mild asphyxia was observed in 4 and 3 patients respectively in group A and B with one patient apiece reporting moderate asphyxia. The difference between the two groups was found to be statistically non-significant (p=0.925). The APGAR scores in the 5th minute also reported similar results with a reduction in patients with mild and moderate asphyxia (p=0.222) [Table 8].

The intraoperative complications reported in the present study showed a significant difference in

distribution between the group with respect to shivering (p=0.018), nystagmus (p=0.021) and sedation (p=0.025) [Table 9].

With regard to return of motor power based on Bromage scale, group A reported a time interval of 2.46 hours and group B 2.52 hours, and these values were found to be comparable (p=0.147). Duration of analgesia was 2 hours 52 minutes in group A and 3 hours 27 minutes in group B with this difference being statistically significant (p=0.000). The total number of analgesia intervention administered postoperatively was assessed with patients in group A requiring 89 interventions with group B patients requiring 76 interventions. However, this difference was not found to be statistically significant (p=0.262). The quantity of administration of diclofenac and tramadol injections was also found to be not significant (p=0.555). The duration of surgery was found to be 1.01±0.15 for group A and 0.97±0.22 for group B and this difference was not found to be significant (p=0.950) [Table 10].

Table 8: APGAR score in the first and fifth minute

	Score	Group A	Group B	Chi square	P Value
1 st Min	Normal	35	36	0.157	0.925
	Mild Asphyxia	4	3		
	Moderate Asphyxia	1	1		
5 th Min	Normal	38	39	3.013	0.222
	Mild Asphyxia	2	0		
	Moderate Asphyxia	0	1		

Table 9: Intraoperative complications

Complication	Group A	Group B	Chi square	P - Value
Nausea	7	8	0.082	0.775
Vomiting	2	4	0.721	0.396
Shivering	11	3	5.541	0.018*
Nystagmus	0	5	5.333	0.021*
Sedation	4	12	5.000	0.025*
Bradycardia	1	0	1.013	0.314

*Statistically significant (p<0.05)

Table 10: Return of motor power

Variables	Group	Values	
Time to achieve bromage scale 0	Group A	2.46	0.147
	Group B	2.52	
Duration of spinal analgesia	Group A	2 '52'	0.000*
	Group B	3 '27'	
Number of analgesic interventions	Group A	89	0.262
	Group B	76	
Duration of surgery	Group A	1.01±0.15	0.345
	Group B	0.97±0.22	

*Statistically significant (p<0.05)

In the study there was no significant difference in analgesics required between two groups [Table 11].

Table 11: Various analgesics required

	Group A	Group B	Chi Square	P Value
Inj. Diclofenac	80	74	3.687	0.055
Inj. Tramadol	9	2		

Discussion

One of the most prevalent obstetric procedures is the cesarean section, with a reported 42.35% global prevalence.[12] A number of additives, at varying concentrations, have been used in conjunction with local anesthetics to reduce their dosage, promote early motor recovery, and lengthen their duration of analgesia. These additions include clonidine, midazolam, fentanyl, ketamine, etc. [13] Research comparing ketamine to other adjuvants, such as tramadol, suggests that ketamine may have unique benefits in terms of analgesic efficacy when paired with bupivacaine, especially in spinal anesthetic settings.[20]

The results of the present showed that the mean age, weight, and height between the two groups was comparable. Time taken for sensory level to reach T5 was 6.15±1.33 for group A and 3.50±1.24 for group B and this difference was found to be statistically highly significant (p=0.000). In a study by Gupta N et al, onset of sensory and motor block was faster in ketamine group as compared to fentanyl group and the difference in the onset time for the two drugs was statistically significant, (p<0.05).[13]

Results related to the incidence of hypotension showed that it was observed mostly among patients in group A when compared to group B and this difference was found to be statistically highly significant (p=0.000) and similar was also observed when assessing the number of episodes of

hypotension between the two groups with group A patients reporting a significantly higher incidence of hypotension (p=0.000). The incidence of hypotension was similar in a previously conducted study where the non-ketamine group showed a significantly higher number of incidences. [10]

With regard to mean SBP, DBP and MAP, a significant difference was observed in the values between the two groups when reported at the 5-minute and 10-minute time points with group B showing higher pressure values (p<0.05). The results of a study by Patil I et al reported that the difference in SBP and DBP between groups treated by bupivacaine alone and bupivacaine along with ketamine was significant at the 10th minute (p<0.05) with the ketamine group showing the higher SBP which is similar to the results of the present study.[10] Similar results with regard to SBP and DBP were also obtained by Alur J et al in their study comparing bupivacaine + ketamine to bupivacaine + Magnesium interventions.[11] SBP and MAP were higher in ketamine group as compared to fentanyl group at 2, 30, 40, 90,120,150 minutes (P value < 0.05) in another previously conducted study.[13]

APGAR score at the first minute and fifth minute showed that mild and moderate asphyxia was observed among a small proportion of patients in both groups which was found to reduce by the fifth minute. However, incidence at both intervals was not statistically significant (p>0.05). Non-significant difference in APGAR scores was also

observed in a previously conducted study which compared the use of ketamine and magnesium as adjuncts to bupivacaine.[11] There was no statistical difference between APGAR score of both ketamine and fentanyl group at 1 and 5 min in another previously conducted study.[13] This was also reported in other studies. [14,15]

The intraoperative complications reported a significant difference in distribution between the groups with respect to shivering ($p=0.018$), nystagmus ($p=0.021$) and sedation ($p=0.025$). The results of a previously conducted study showed that nystagmus and sedation were more common in the ketamine group which was similar to that obtained in the present study.[10] When compared to bupivacaine alone, the incidence of side effects, such as nausea or sedation scores, was not substantially higher with the addition of ketamine. This implies that the mixture is safe to use in this situation in addition to being effective. [18,19]

Based on the Bromage scale, patients from group A (2.46 hours) showed a return of motor power faster than group B patients (2.52 hours) but this difference was not significant, this result was similar to that obtained in a previously conducted study wherein the time to achieve Bromage scale 0 was 2.66 ± 0.12 and 2.7 ± 0.13 between the non-ketamine and ketamine groups respectively.[10]

Duration of analgesia was 2 hours 52 minutes in group A and 3 hours 27 minutes in group B with this difference being statistically significant ($p=0.000$) and this was similar to that obtained in a previous study wherein the duration was 2.19 ± 0.15 hours for non-ketamine groups and 3.50 ± 2.1 hours for the ketamine group.[10] It has been demonstrated that ketamine added to bupivacaine extends the duration of analgesia. Comparing the combination to bupivacaine alone, a systematic review found that both the motor and sensory blockade durations increased significantly, with effect sizes indicating substantial clinical relevance (e.g., sensory blockade time increased by roughly 39.73 minutes).[17]

The total number of analgesia intervention administered postoperatively was assessed with patients in group A requiring 89 interventions with group B patients requiring 76 interventions. However, this difference was not found to be statistically significant ($p=0.262$). The quantity of administration of diclofenac and tramadol injections was also found to be not significant ($p=0.555$). Research has shown that ketamine and bupivacaine together lower postoperative pain levels and the total amount of analgesics needed. Patients who received bupivacaine plus ketamine in a randomized clinical trial showed reduced pain scores at different time points after surgery in

comparison to those who received bupivacaine alone.[16]

The duration of surgery was found to be 1.01 ± 0.15 for group A and 0.97 ± 0.22 for group B and this difference was not found to be significant ($p=0.950$) This was similar to the results obtained in a previously conducted study which reported that the duration of surgery was 61.24 ± 5.29 minutes in the non-ketamine group and 60.72 ± 4.07 minutes in the ketamine group.

The limitations of the present study include the single centered nature of the study as well as the limited age range that was involved in the study. This study's strengths were using well-researched, widely accessible, and safe study medications at the recommended dosages, doing the surgeries in a single location, and having a single, blinded investigator gather postoperative data. The results of the present study help in adding to evidence on the effectiveness of adding ketamine to bupivacaine in patients undergoing cesarean section which can help improve upon its present use. The use of ketamine has been shown to not result in any danger to the mother or child which can help obstetricians in providing quality care and further help in faster recovery of the patient.

Conclusion

The results of the present study help conclude that onset of sensory block was found to be more rapid by adding ketamine to intrathecal bupivacaine. With regard to complications encountered, incidence of hypotension and bradycardia are much less after adding ketamine to intrathecal bupivacaine. There were no neonatal side effects on adding ketamine to intrathecal bupivacaine. These help in ascertaining that ketamine addition to intrathecal bupivacaine is an effective and safe way to reduce postoperative pain among patients undergoing cesarean section.

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